

An Auto-Ethnobiography on the Life of Auto Mechanics

Romar C. Ignacio

Bulacan State University, Bustos Campus, Bulacan, Philippines
romar.ignacio@bulsu.edu.ph

Publication Date: August 2024

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13340625>

ABSTRACT

This paper narrates the life of auto mechanics which have been unnoticed for a long time as evidenced by the lack of literature that can be found. Using an Auto-Ethnobiography method of qualitative research, the author shows the life and experiences of auto mechanics in the Philippines, both in the casa and talyer set-up. By providing these experiences and life of the subjects, a glimpse of the hardships and difficulties can be seen with an integration of the experiences of the author, who is also part of the industry.

Keywords: Automotive, Auto Mechanics, Auto-Ethnobiography, Philippine Automotive Industry

Suggested Citation:

Ignacio, R. (2024). An Auto-Ethnobiography on the Life of Auto Mechanics. *International Journal on Culture, History, and Religion*, 6(2), 53-59 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13340625>

Introduction

Transportation has become an essential part of our day-to-day experience. How people travel from place to place has drastically changed and developed from carriages and horses to automobiles that use machines and technology. This improvement in the means of transportation for the people also helped the development of society. The rise of the car or automotive industry began in the 1860s and 1870s through the development of the gasoline engine, mainly in France and Germany (Jahanshahi et al., 2011). In the early 20th century, manufacturers from Germany and France were joined by the British, Italian, and American makers. The term “automotive industry” refers to all businesses and endeavors in producing motor vehicles. This includes most car parts, such as bodywork and engines, while excluding gasoline, tires, and batteries. The principal products of the automotive industry are passenger automobiles for public transportation and light trucks, pickups, vans, and sport utility vehicles for commercial and personal use (Shamkris Global Group, n.d.).

Automotive engines that use gasoline and diesel engines need parts or repairs and regular maintenance. Thus, the importance of auto mechanics cannot be separated from the Car industry. The growth of mass manufacturing and the corporations manufacturing automobiles and their engines throughout Asia and Europe have increased the auto mechanic industries, technologies, and skills needed for associated repair, parts, and maintenance.

Conner and Thoman (1975) defined an auto mechanic as a mechanic who provides services and repairs in the automotive field. They focus on automobiles, sometimes specializing in one or more automobile brands or moreso working with any brand. Their car fixing services mainly involve diagnosing and repairing the problem accurately and quickly. As per definition, Auto mechanics play an essential role in keeping vehicles running properly. It is a worthwhile occupation choice, not for everyone but rewarding to some. Auto mechanics are essential because they provide a vital service and business that keeps cars in good working order. Their importance is further demonstrated by the

fact that they are crucial to the growth and survival of the transportation sector in general and the car sector in particular as long as people continue to choose mass transit for their personal mobility needs.

Automotive mechanics have all-around duties and responsibilities that they perform in the service department of car dealerships. They always need to improve and upgrade their skills and knowledge to cater to the customers’ needs or concerns about their automobile unit. Despite their hardships, auto mechanics working in small auto shops receive a bare minimum salary and fewer incentives or commissions. However, if the auto shop has many customers, the shop owner gives them incentives or additional payments aside from their regular salary. Most automotive mechanics gain experience in their workplace for quite a period of time. Many mechanics choose to work abroad for a better salary.

Meanwhile, auto mechanics working in branded car dealerships are well compensated and have enough benefits compared to those working in small local shops. Auto mechanics render an eight-hour shift daily with only one rest day per week. Because they are employed in a branded company, they are able to utilize the latest tools and equipment to service their customers. These tools and equipment include the use of different special tools and electronic devices for troubleshooting and diagnosing to repair or maintain the engine quality of the cars. They have access to the repair manuals that the manufacturers give for easy instructions and procedures on troubleshooting, finding the parts, naming, and repairing parts. These auto mechanics working in car dealers enjoy their work because of the good facilities, complete tools and equipment, and different skills training provided by the company. Most of them are sent to car manufacturing plants and take up training for a month for free, yet they are paid for their training. For instance, companies like Toyota, Mitsubishi, and Nissan send their auto mechanics to take short courses to upgrade their knowledge and skills and become certified auto mechanics. Many of the auto mechanics who have served for a long time in the company were promoted to positions like supervisor or manager, especially those who are college graduates.

Many things still need to be known about the life of auto mechanics, especially here in the Philippines, where many auto repair shops can be seen along the roads and highways. Thus, this paper aims to provide an auto-ethnobiography narrative to share and reflect on the experiences of auto mechanics as the automotive industry develops together with the mechanics. The researcher would like to see the lives of auto mechanics and how their works differ from one another. Through this, a new perspective may be seen in the context of auto mechanics because of the limited literature on their lives and experiences.

The Auto Mechanics in the Car Industry

According to Rowe (2019), present repair facilities technicians specialize in automotive services to continue repairing and maintaining 21st-century or modern vehicles. In the past, these positions primarily had the ability to diagnose and repair mechanical systems. Even though today's technicians still require abundant mechanical skills, they must also be proficient in diagnosing and repairing electronic, hydraulic, and pneumatic systems on today's new vehicles. Modern vehicles now contain advanced navigation systems with satellite communication technology capable of notifying the driver of traffic issues and broadcasting verbal directions to the driver. The same navigation system can provide access to a Global Positioning System (GPS), allowing the vehicle's position on the earth to be located accurately and enabling stolen vehicle recovery, internet access, and communication. The vehicle's computerized network can notify the driver and the dealers of any vehicle's electronic system needing maintenance or repair. Modern vehicles also use a collision avoidance system that automatically applies the brakes, eliminating a collision or minimizing vehicle damage or personal injury. Automotive repair technicians repairing modern vehicles must have an understanding of basic physics, chemistry, mathematics, fluid dynamics, electrical theory, computer operation and networking, and heat transfer, in addition to being proficient in performing basic automotive repair practices.

The auto mechanics in car dealerships have

advantages over other automotive repair shops. Most auto mechanic employees have a minimum salary that is even higher than this, depending on the qualifications and skills they learn from many years of experience. Most auto mechanics in the car dealership have similarities in their nature and business process. The auto mechanics in some branded dealerships require applicants to be at least TESDA graduates and NC II holders. Even if applicants are not experienced mechanics, they are welcome to apply and have a chance to be employed. The salary is minimum wage, but if they have years of experience, it is even higher than the entry salary grade. The training the employees enjoy yearly depends on the release of the new model cars. Most often, auto mechanics working in branded automotive dealerships enjoy the best tools, equipment, and facilities for servicing customers, not counting the incentives and commissions they receive.

As an automotive mechanic, I was employed as an auto mechanic at Rapide Auto Service Center and Grupo Uvero Incorporated Auto Care Center; both are local automotive repair shops. I was assigned to the different areas or services in this shop. As a beginner in the field, I was assigned to easier jobs such as changing engine oils, gear oils, transmission fluids, coolant, and brake fluids. As my experience in doing my job developed my skills, I was given another responsibility, such as providing preventive maintenance services to check and evaluate the condition of our clients' automobiles. Different tasks were given to me as they see me fit, and I have gained more experience in auto mechanics. When my second employer saw me fit to do tasks more than what I was doing in the previous one, I performed more difficult tasks for the customers. I then do major services in the shop, like overhauling gasoline and diesel engines and replacing timing belts and chains. I also perform under-chassis services such as replacing the shock absorber, bushing, ball joint, stabilizer link, and bar in the brake system. My tasks include fixing the steering system, such as overhauling rack and pinion and gearbox, power steering pump, and diagnosing steering and indicator lights. From an entry-level salary as a beginner in the automotive field, my salary increased because of the skills and knowledge I gained through experience. In

my 16 years of experience as an auto mechanic, I have a lot of experience daily and make sure that my knowledge and skills are always renewed for me to upgrade my level of skills to render different services in the shop and when taking home service. I have not yet seen myself satisfied with this skill set because technology keeps changing from one time to another. So, as auto mechanics, we should always stay updated and upgrade our knowledge for this technology transition. I plan to be a successful auto mechanic as the experience always adds to my life because, being an auto mechanic, I earn money and help as the source of income for my family and for our future.

Auto Mechanics and their Skills Training

Typical auto mechanics came from different experiences in auto repair shops. Most auto mechanics are graduates of college or vocational courses such as TESDA. Many of the new and younger auto mechanics graduate senior high school under the Technical Vocation Strand. They are equipped with knowledge and skills for them to learn. As the world progresses and the automotive field becomes more high-tech, the education and experience of auto mechanics are being weighed for employment. That is why, aside from their education and training, they need to have actual work experience in the field to test their knowledge and skills, such as on-the-job training or immersion programs in their schools. In other cases, new employees are being assisted and trained by senior auto mechanics to become capable of doing the tasks properly. It is normal in auto repair shops for senior auto mechanics to share their knowledge and skills with beginners or those who want to learn other tasks. Furthermore, many auto mechanics became interested in the field because of their family, relatives, or friends. Some have their family-owned repair shops, while others have friends working as auto mechanics. Few may have become interested in auto mechanics because of their passion for collecting cars.

Improving Tools and Equipment

As technology progresses, tools and equipment in auto mechanics become more and more noteworthy since the demand in the car industry

for efficient maintenance, repairs, and diagnostics, as well as innovations and improvements, not to mention the aesthetics to promote convenience and style of riding public or customers are necessary. In Hitachi, India, they constantly consider this factor in making the car industry viable and responsive to the needs of the riding customers and efficient mobility (KARREP, 2022).

Auto mechanics are always inseparable from their tools and equipment; it is as if their weapon is performing different services to their customers. It is common for each mechanic to have their own set of basic tools for repair. They usually use hand tools as common tools for the job, and these are low-cost and easy-to-use tools for basic repair and services. Meanwhile, other bigger and more expensive tools, known as power tools, are helpful for more difficult jobs for auto mechanics. These tools are operated by electric motors that simple mechanics or small repair shop owners cannot acquire. This led some owners of small shops to fabricate cheaper equipment and tools, and sometimes they improvise tools to work like those expensive ones. In local repair shops, you will notice that many of their tools are fabricated or improvised, but they can still offer good services to their clients.

The automotive field benefitted greatly from colleges and universities with the help of the students' output from their thesis works. This may be seen as a great help for small-time auto mechanics because many of the outputs produced by colleges and universities are fabricated or improvised power tools that may cost less and/or work better than the original ones. It may seem to be simple outputs for compliance with the students' degrees, but every innovation done or proposed in colleges and universities is a great help for small-time auto mechanics and the entire automotive field.

Auto Mechanics and Technology

As rapid technological advancements happen in our society, the improvement of the car industry also develops not only in its parts but also in its improved automobile features and systems. According to Denis John (2023), the auto mechanic industry, also known as the repair trade,

may have begun with simple diagnostic tools that have evolved over time to more sophisticated computerized systems. Given the rapid rise in the popularity of electric and hybrid vehicles, modern auto repairs will also continue to grow significantly due to technological advancements.

Auto repair shop management software has been introduced to the industry to process auto mechanic work systematically. This would further guarantee that mechanics have the resources necessary, such as their tools and skills, in this day of rapid technological innovation to identify and address automotive issues. This means that auto mechanics and repair shops will stay and play importantly in the car industry's maintenance and sustainability as they address the mobility of people, goods, and services (John, 2023).

Nowadays, auto mechanics adapt to the technologies used in different automobile models in this generation. There are many of the latest technologies that auto mechanics depend on and use. Most of the technology is used all over the automobile system in automobiles, such as the engine, under chassis, power train, sensors, and electrical and electronics systems of the automobile units. The common technology is the On Board Diagnostic Tools used by auto mechanics to troubleshoot the check engine lights, transmission, powertrain, and even the electrical and electronics trouble in the unit. This computer image is used to plug in the driver-side USB port and diagnose the warning lights on in the dashboard to help the auto mechanic in the manual diagnosis of the unit, which is even time wasted. Another example of the technology used is the lifter and computerized wheel alignment, which makes the lifting and alignment service comfortable and hassle-free. This also makes the auto mechanic safe when performing the task under chassis and in engine services. There is also the presence of power tools that operate the pressurized fluid and air and are controlled by the electric motor. Most of the tools or hand tools are being designed and adapted to this technology, which makes the work comfortable and avoids injury at the same time. However, the importance of the people who can work without high-technology tools and equipment, or only use bare-hand tools to work manually, is probably the best experience, and it has different advantages. These well-trained auto

mechanics, who are experts in manual repairs, are efficient even without electricity.

My experiences using high-technology tools and equipment have helped me a lot when diagnosing and troubleshooting automobile units. Having and using high-technology tools and equipment to diagnose problems attracts more customers. These tools and equipment helped me work with ease and earn more money because that kind of diagnosis is in demand due to their capacity to update the system of automobiles. The high-technology features in auto repairs, including lifters and machines, are helping auto mechanics perform better, faster, and accurately with ease and safety. Hence, when we speak of the technology used by auto mechanics, whether in big or branded repair shops or in small local repair shops, we have different points of view to consider. Those mechanics who can do things manually have an edge when tools, equipment, and electricity are unavailable. However, those who have and can use high-technology tools and equipment have a better chance of doing work with ease and faster.

Auto Mechanics in the Local Auto Repair Shops

According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (2023), almost half a million employees work in car repair shops in our country as of the year 2021. This number is growing for sure because many people own vehicles now, not just buying brand new cars that need less repairs but also those who are buying secondhand cars that need a lot of repairs. Because of the increasing number of secondhand car owners, not all of them can avail themselves of services from the service providers of their car's brand. Thus, they tend to go to local auto repair shops that are available in their areas. These local auto repair shops offer cheaper services yet with experienced mechanics who can fix their cars. Locally, people call these small local auto repair shops as "talyer". Franchise Market Philippines (2022) mentioned that a talyer alludes to the sloppy and coordinated help and mechanics shop. Talyer is from the Spanish "taller" which implies studio. At the beginning of the auto business in the Philippines, there were just two sorts of administration shops: casa and talyer. A casa is known as the service

center of the automobile brand, which gives services to the car owners of their brand. Any shop that was not Casa was a talyer. Today, Filipinos refer to unorganized neighborhood service and repair businesses as talyer. They additionally applied to coordinated assistance and fix chain shops.

In the experience of talyer auto mechanics, their experiences and skills are considered for the tasks to be given to them. They receive the right amount of salary. Many of them work and are paid per day without any mandatory government contributions and benefits. Their salary depends on their skills and capacity to work. Some of them are paid based on the number of automobiles repaired. These benefits are far lower than those received by auto mechanics working in casas or branded auto repair shops. Though the expertise of those working in talyers can be seen as equal to that of those working in casas, and yet customers pay cheaper, it is recognizable that their work environments are less safe than those in casas. They wear any clothing they want as long as they are comfortable working compared with those in casas who wear uniforms that sometimes limit their movements. Talyer mechanics are also enjoying a less strict environment because during the times that they do not have customers, they can use cellphones or watch television compared to those in casas who cannot do it.

Since I became an auto mechanic, I have experienced the hardships endured by those working in local auto repair shops or talyers. I know how difficult it is to work, especially if you have few skills and no background experience in auto repair. Talyers are good breeding grounds for those who want to improve their skills and have experience in auto repairs before applying to casas. My work as an auto mechanic in talyers does not limit me to having sideline jobs like home service car repairs, as long as I am not competing with the talyer. Such experience working in a talyer shows the real hardships of auto mechanics who started from nothing to achieving great skills and knowledge in the automotive field.

Conclusion

In the field of automotive, auto mechanics play an important role in ensuring the safety of

the people by keeping the automobiles in good condition. Despite the increasing number of cars on the roads and the rampant release of new models every year, auto mechanics are unnoticed by many because they do the hard labor and are always backstage in the automotive field. Their hardships, whether they work in a talyer or a casa, remain unnoticed, yet they are very enthusiastic in their job. Their skills and experiences are things that machines and technology cannot fully replace. Despite the increasing demand for high-technology tools and equipment, the auto mechanics' expertise is far more important and useful. Given that most of them are not degree holders, their job is essential to the industry itself because of the increasing number of car owners and users who seek to ensure that their cars are running well and well. May this attempt for an auto-ethnobiography on auto mechanics set good precedence in looking after the role and life of auto mechanics as they are the front liners of the automotive industry.

References

- Conner, M., & Thoman, L. (1975). An Analysis of the Auto Mechanic Occupation. ERIC. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED107949>
- Franchise Market Philippines. (2022). Automotive industry in the Philippines - statistics & facts. FranchiseMarket.PH. <https://www.franchisemarket.ph/blog/automotive-business>
- Jahanshahi, A.A., Gashti, M.A.H., Mirdamadi, S.A., Nawaser, K., & Khaksar, S.M. (2011). Study of the Effects of Customer Service and Product Quality on Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science* 1(7). 253-260. [https://www.ijhssnet.com/view.php?u=https://www.ijhssnet.com/journals/Vol._1_No._7_\[Special_Issue_June_2011\]/33.pdf](https://www.ijhssnet.com/view.php?u=https://www.ijhssnet.com/journals/Vol._1_No._7_[Special_Issue_June_2011]/33.pdf)
- John, D. (2023, June 29). The Role of Technology in Modern Car Repairs. Dennis Piper. Retrieved August 10, 2024, from <https://blogs.oregonstate.edu/piperde/2023/06/29/the-role-of-technology-in-modern-car-repairs/>
- KARREP. (2022, December 7). Tools and Equipment Used in Automotive Industry. KARREP. <https://karrep.com/tools-and-equipment-used-in-automotive-industry>

- Philippine Statistics Authority. (2023, October 7). 2021 Annual Survey of Philippine Business and Industry (ASPBI) - Wholesale and Retail Trade; Repair of Motor Vehicles and Motorcycles Section: Final Results | Philippine Statistics Authority | Republic of the Philippines. Philippine Statistics Authority. <https://www.psa.gov.ph/content/2021-annual-survey-philippine-business-and-industry-aspbi-wholesale-and-retail-trade-repair>
- Rowe, B. G. (2019). Job satisfaction of Automotive technicians: A comparison of graduates from General Programs to Manufacturer-Sponsored Programs [Dissertation, Liberty University]. In Scholars Crossing. <https://digitalcommons.liberty.edu/doctoral/2267/>
- Shamkris Global Group. (n.d.). Automotive Industry. Retrieved August 10, 2024, from <https://licenseinindia.com/automotive/>